

NATURE AND TYPES OF INNOVATION IN THE MODERNIZATION OF
THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: In the context of modernization of the national economy, the wider attraction of innovations, especially foreign ones, into the economy of our republic will make an important contribution to ensuring the effective implementation of economic reforms being implemented in our country. This becomes all the more relevant as it increases attention to assessing the effectiveness of innovative projects implemented in the national economy.

Key words: Innovation, modernization, investment, national economy, competition, innovative activity, economic approach.

Innovation policy is one of the main directions of economic development of any country and expansion of production in it. Therefore, comprehensive development of the national economy requires an active innovation policy. This, in turn, ensures the implementation of deep structural changes in the republic. Activation of the flow of foreign and domestic investments into the spheres of the national economy is the main factor that initiates a new stage of economic growth. Accordingly, active economic development requires large-scale innovation. Therefore, innovation is the force that drives any economy and ensures its development. It is important for any country to achieve prosperity by using its capabilities and increasing the volume of innovations directed to its economy.

The economic development of developed countries shows that it is difficult to imagine the development of the economy of any country without innovation. "Innovation". Also, innovation refers to material (intangible) benefits introduced

into production and non-production objects, the capital invested in the objects of their business activity, that is, to achieve a positive economic effect.

Effective use of innovation directly depends on the correct expression of its essence. In the literature, the concept of "innovation" is interpreted differently

Innovation means introduction of new products as a result of practical (scientific-technical) assimilation of new products, innovations include new products, science-demanding technological processes, modification of products and services (social innovations).

It is known that the transition from one quality to another requires energy, time, money and similar resources. The process of transferring news to innovation is also mainly carried out through the consumption of various resources such as investment and time. As a system of economic relations under market conditions, innovation and investment are the main components of innovative activity in the pre-sale of goods in the framework of demand, supply and price formation. Innovation forms the innovation market, investment-capital market (investment), innovation (innovation)-pure competition market, they are presented in diagram 1.

The objective need to increase production efficiency and competitiveness in market conditions serves as a motivation for scientific and technical renewal of the material basis of economic systems.

Its manifestation is represented by the high potential efficiency of implementation of innovative opportunities. Therefore, the primary task of the state is to create the main internal and external motives that invite the enterprise to innovative activity as a factor of economic growth.

In order to carry out innovative activities in a production enterprise, it is necessary to have the innovative potential of the enterprise, which is described as the sum of various resources, as well as:

- intellectual (technological document, patents, license, business plan for assimilation of innovations, enterprise innovation program);

- material (experience-equipment base, technological equipment, field resources);
- financial (personal, loan, investment, etc.);
- related to personnel (leader-innovator, personnel, interested in innovations; cooperation and personal relations of employees with ITIs and HEIs);
- infrastructure (new product marketing department, patent-legal department, information department, etc.).

It is an axiom of market relations that production efficiency depends on its technical level. Objectively, competitive struggle is also an axiom of market relations. Objective competitive struggle is the main incentive for innovative activity that increases the technical and technological level of production.

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